

SND Policy for the Review of Data and Metadata

Date: 2025-11-24

Version: 3 (translation)

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SND policy for the review of data and metadata

SND aims to ensure that data and metadata shared through SND's services are well described and have high compliance with the FAIR principles.¹ To achieve this, data and metadata shared through SND's tool DORIS must undergo a review before they are published and made available in the catalogue on Researchdata.se. The review process examines the data, metadata, and documentation with regard to how usable, understandable, and well-documented they are, but does *not* assess their scientific quality.

This policy applies to data and metadata that are described and shared through DORIS for publication in the Researchdata.se catalogue. The policy has been adopted by SND's Steering Committee on 28 September 2021, with revisions in 2024 and 2025. It is implemented on all new catalogue entries as of 28 September 2021.

1. Data and metadata that are described and shared through DORIS shall, as far as possible, comply with the FAIR principles as they are applied in the research field for which the data material has been produced.
2. Data and metadata that are described and shared through DORIS shall be reviewed according to the principles outlined in the document *Requirements and Recommendations for Data and Metadata Described and Shared through DORIS*.² It is of particular importance that no data are shared in violation of current legislation.
3. Members of the SND Network who have local data storage at their respective organizations are responsible for the data and metadata shared through DORIS. Organizations with local storage may choose to independently review and publish data descriptions; in such cases, the SND Office will provide support as needed.
4. For data stored at SND CARE,³ the review shall be carried out by staff at the SND Office. Where data belong to an organization that is a member of the SND Network, the review may be conducted jointly by staff at the organization responsible for the data and the SND Office.⁴ In joint reviews, SND's role is to ensure that the requirements (see 2, above) are met and to provide advice during the review process.
5. The SND Policy for Persistent Identifiers on Datasets shall be followed.⁵

¹ FAIR means that research data shall be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Read more at e.g., [FORCE11](#) or the [Swedish Research Council](#).

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6351363>

³ SND CARE is SND's certified repository. Use of SND CARE is governed by a service agreement.

⁴ The organization responsible for the data determines when they are ready to be included in the review process.

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6352451>

6. SND aims to complete the review of data and metadata within one week of the submission of a data description. Where more curation is needed or if the researcher needs to supply additional information, the review may take longer. If possible, researchers' specific requests for an expedited review process shall be accommodated.
7. Considerations, discussions, and decisions made during the review process shall be documented and preserved with the data description. It is of particular importance to document assessments of whether the data contain personal data or other protected information, and assessments concerning the chosen level of access to the data.